

Zinc(II)-NN¹-Di(thiocarbamoyl)hydrazinate Complex and Its Adduct with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

BISWESWAR DAS and P. C. ROY

Department of Chemistry, Government College, Rourkela-769 004

Manuscript received 29 March 1982, revised 2 March 1983, accepted 20 May 1983

Zinc(II)-NN¹-di(thiocarbamoyl)hydrazinate and its adduct with nitrogen donor ligands are isolated and characterised by their elemental analysis, molar conductance and ir spectral studies. The ir spectra of zinc(II)-NN¹-di(thiocarbamoyl)hydrazinate show that both sulphur and nitrogen are bonded to the metal forming 4 coordinated complex and the nitrogen donor ligands form 5 coordinated adduct.

It has been shown¹⁻³ that NN¹-di(thiocarbamoyl)hydrazinate or dithiourea (DTU) acts as a chelating agent. It is reported that dithiourea undergoes enolisation and functions as a dibasic and possibly a tetradentate ligand³. Satapathy and co-workers have shown recently that dithiourea behaves as a weak dibasic acid in aqueous solution⁴. In the present communication we report the preparation of inner metallic complexes of Zn(II)-dithiourea and its adduct with nitrogen donor ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either B.D.H. or E. Merck products. The purity of the complexes were established by determining metal, nitrogen and sulphur contents. The organic chelating agent dithiourea was prepared by the literature method⁵.

Preparation of zinc(II)-dithiourea: Sodium salt of dithiourea was treated with hot aqueous solution of Zn(II) chloride in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The solution

was stirred continuously for about 15 min when a complex appeared which was allowed to settle. The precipitate was heated over water bath for 1 hr and suction filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of Zn(DTU)L (L=pyridine, dimethylamine, diethylamine, ethylene diamine): Zn(DTU) in ethanol was mixed with the respective ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. The solution was kept overnight and then treated with ethanol when the complexes separated out. The complexes were suction filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of Zn(DTU)L (L=α-, β-, γ-picoline, or quinoline): Zn(DTU) in ethanol was mixed with the respective ligand in 1 : 1 molar ratio and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr when a precipitate appeared. The precipitate was cooled, suction filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, M. P. AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEX OF Zn(II)

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour and form	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/Calcd.)			Δ _M (mbos)
				Zinc	Nitrogen	Sulphur	
1.	Zn(DTU)	Yellowish crystalline	182	30.10 (30.04)	25.50 (25.72)	29.25 (29.40)	1.2
2.	Zn(DTU)Py	White crystalline	196	22.20 (22.03)	23.75 (23.59)	21.40 (21.53)	2.4
3.	Zn(DTU)α-Pic	Greenish crystalline	198 d	21.00 (21.04)	22.65 (22.52)	20.50 (20.59)	2.0
4.	Zn(DTU)β-Pic	Light pink crystalline	202 d	21.15 (21.04)	22.70 (22.52)	20.45 (20.59)	2.2
5.	Zn(DTU)γ-Pic	Light grey crystalline	200 d	21.10 (21.04)	22.45 (22.52)	20.45 (20.59)	2.2
6.	Zn(DTU)DMA	Yellowish white crystalline	185 d	26.70 (26.9)	28.70 (28.80)	26.20 (26.37)	2.5
7.	Zn(DTU)DEA	Yellowish white crystalline	174	24.00 (24.15)	25.60 (25.80)	23.00 (23.25)	3.0
8.	Zn(DTU)EDA	Light yellow crystalline	197	25.00 (25.36)	27.00 (27.16)	24.72 (24.80)	3.5
9.	Zn(DTU)Quin	Faint yellow crystalline	210	21.32 (21.04)	25.56 (25.52)	20.32 (20.54)	3.4
10.	DTU	Yellowish white crystalline	220	—	37.10 (37.30)	41.95 (42.60)	2.8

d=The complex decomposes above this temp.

Zinc was estimated⁶ gravimetrically as tetrapyrroline-zinc-thiocyanate, nitrogen was estimated⁷ by modified Kjeldahl's method and sulphur was estimated⁸ gravimetrically by alkali fusion method. Conductance measurements were carried out with $10^{-3}M$ solution in dimethylformamide using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, model CLOI/OIA with a dip type cell. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in the range $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The m.p., analysis and molar conductance data are recorded in Table 1 and ir spectral data in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Ligand H ₂ DTU	Zn(DTU)	Zn(DTU)Py	Zn(DTU)κ-Pic
3350 s	3368 sbd	3320 s	3120 s
2400 m	—	—	—
1610 s	1600 s	1610 s	1605 s
1600 s	—	—	—
1545 s	1510 s	1515 s	1520 s
1375	1310	1320	1330
1300-1340 wbd	—	—	—
1180	1125	1120	1120
1055	—	—	—
840	—	—	—
790	765	725	725

Complexes of zincdithiurea with other nitrogen ligands have also significantly shifted.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are white or bright coloured crystals differing from the parent compound Zn(DTU) in appearance. Elemental analysis of the complexes correspond to the composition Zn(DTU)L (L = nitrogen donor ligand) or Zn(DTU)L₂ (in case of ethylene diamine adduct). They have high melting points, are insoluble in water and alcohol, but soluble in dimethylformamide in which the molar conductance value is very low (Table 1) suggesting non-ionic nature of the complexes.

The infrared spectra indicate (Table 2) that bands at 3350 cm^{-1} in the ligand is not significantly shifted in the complexes. This indicates that coordination of ligands has not taken place through the nitrogen of NH₂ group. The bands observed at ~ 1610 and 1545 cm^{-1} in dithiurea are due to deformation vibration of NH₂ group as (C-N) stretching vibrations. The latter is shifted to around $\sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while the former remains undisturbed in the complexes indicating the coordination of azido nitrogen with the metal ion. The band at $\sim 2400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of dithiurea is attributable to $\nu(\text{S-H})^9$ vibrations. This band is absent in the complexes suggesting that coordination has also taken place through sulphur atom. The band near 1400 cm^{-1} in the ligand, which is assigned^{10,11} as (C-S) stretching frequency, has been lowered to about 1300 cm^{-1} showing thereby that the sulphur atom of C-S group is involved in coordination. In addition to these a strong band is observed at 790 cm^{-1} in the ligand attributable to coupled bands

of $\nu(\text{C-S})$ and $\nu(\text{C-N})$. This is shifted to lower frequency region ($\sim 765\text{ cm}^{-1}$) clearly indicating the coordination of the ligand to the metal ion through both sulphur and nitrogen atoms. Besides that, the nitrogen donor ligand (L) bands have also been modified in the complexes indicating that the ligands also have been bonded to the metal ion.

On the basis of these analytical and infrared spectral data of the complexes it is suggested that dithiurea is bonded to zinc(II) through sulphur and nitrogen forming four coordinated complexes whereas its adduct with nitrogen donor ligands (except ethylene diamine) forms five coordinated complexes and EDA forms six coordinated complex. The correct structure of five coordinated complexes whether trigonal, bipyramidal or square bipyramidal can be ascertained from X-ray studies.

Structure of the ligand and complex : The ligand may be postulated to exist in any of the following three structural forms.

The ir spectrum of the ligand shows a number of N-H stretching vibrations in the 3200 cm^{-1} region and at 1620 cm^{-1} attributed to NH₂ deformation. Since the band at 1620 cm^{-1} is not expected for structure (III), the existence of the ligand in this form is ruled out. So we believe that the ligand exists in equilibrium in the (I) and (II) tautomeric forms.

On the basis of their findings from acid dissociation measurements, ir and electronic spectra, Satapathy⁴ and co-worker also believe in the above keto-enol tautomeric forms of the ligand.

Considering the *trans* structure of the ligand to be more stable than the *cis* form and the tetradentate behaviour of the ligand, we suggest the following probable structure of the complex.

The best structure and whether these five coordinated complexes are trigonal, bipyramidal or square bipyramidal can be ascertained from X-ray studies.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. G. B. Behera, Head, Chemistry Department, Sambalpur University for kindly recording the ir spectra and to Dr. K. C. Satapathy, Sambalpur University for valuable discussions.

References

1. A. AHMED DUTTA and P. K. MANDAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1633.
2. A. AHMED DUTTA and P. K. MANDAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2847.
3. R. A. BAILEY, I. R. FEINS and T. R. PETERSON, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 171.
4. K. C. SATAPATHY and T. I. MAHANA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1173.
5. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARYA and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 753.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", 1978, p. 489.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", 1961, p. 256.
8. H. T. CLARKE, "A Hand Book of Organic Analysis Quantitative and Qualitative", 1962, p. 307.
9. L. J. BELLAMY, "Advanced Infrared Group Frequencies", Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1968, p. 117.
10. K. SWAMINATHAN and H. M. N. H. IRVING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1291.
11. R. W. OLLIFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2036.